

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-2

TRANSLATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN AND BASIC MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY CLASSES

Sharipov Bobur Salimovich

Assistant teacher Department of Languages, Samarkand State Medical University

ABSTRACT. The article is devoted to the issues of teaching the Latin language and the basics of medical terminology at a medical institute. The author believes that the training of highly qualified specialists who speak special terminology requires knowledge of a certain number of words of Latin and Greek origin. Based on practical lessons in Latin, he examines the features of the translation of complex and derived clinical terms.

KEY WORDS: medical terminology, Latin language, clinical terminology, term element, Latin and Greek term elements, prefix-suffix derivatives

INTRODUCTION

One of the important tasks of training at a medical institute is the training of highly qualified specialists who are proficient in special terminology. Terminology is a set of terms used in a certain field of knowledge. A term (terminus "limit, boundary") is a word or phrase that serves to unambiguously and accurately designate (name) a special, scientific concept in a certain system of special concepts (in science, technology, production). Like any common noun, a term has content, or meaning (semantics, from the Greek *semantikos* - meaning), and a form, or sound complex (pronunciation, spelling).

While studying at a medical institute, a student encounters a variety of private terminologies of various biomedical and clinical disciplines, which are designed to help him master the modern scientific language of his profession. In a doctor's speech, from 50 to 80% of words of Latin and Greek origin are used.

MAIN PART

The study of clinical terminology in Latin classes is based on the analysis of individual components, called term elements.

A term element is a word-forming element (root, stem, prefix, suffix), which, having a constant meaning, forms a term of one semantic series. The division of a term-word into term elements does not always coincide with its division into morphemes, since some term elements represent a whole block - a combination of two or three morphemes into one whole: prefix + root, root + suffix, prefix + root + suffix. For example, in the term *asthenopia* we isolate the "block" term element *astheno-* (*astheno-*), from the Greek. weak (*a-* - not, without + *sthenos* strength).

Knowledge of term elements allows students to understand many medical terms, for example, 150 terms are formed from the term element *blood haemo-*, *haemato-*, *-aemia*.

Among the term elements we distinguish:

- 1) Greek root term elements that are equivalent to Latin anatomical names, for example, *vertebra* - *spondylos* - *vertebra*, *ae f*, *mouth* - *stoma* - *os,oris n*;
- 2) final term elements that denote pathological changes in organs and tissues, surgical intervention, methods of diagnostic examination or treatment, for example, *-tomia* - operation of dissection, opening of an organ, *-ptosis* - prolapse, displacement of an organ;

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-2

3) affixes (prefixes, suffixes), which also carry some information, for example, syn-, sym- together with something, connection, interaction, -itis - inflammation.

There are initial term elements: stetho- (breast), osteo- (bone), melo- (cheek), noso- (disease) and final term elements: -malacia (abnormal softness), -plastica (reconstructive plastic surgery), -stomia (surgical operation of making a hole), -schisis (splitting of an organ), -centesis (puncture, puncture), but some of them are found at the beginning and at the end of the term: gnathalgia (neuralgia of the jaw), prognathia (protrusion of the upper jaw forward). Some final term elements can be used as an independent term, for example, ptosis, is f - ptosis, drooping of the upper eyelid, gastroptosis, is f - gastroptosis, drooping of the stomach.

One of the tasks of teaching the Latin language and the basics of medical terminology is to master the skills of isolating individual term elements and ways of constructing derivatives and complex terms, since most of the clinical terminology is derivative and complex words.

Derived words consist of a prefix and a root; prefix, root and suffix or root and suffix: arthrit-itis - inflammation of the joint, pan-arthrit-itis - inflammation of all tissues of the joint or all joints, arthr-osis - a chronic disease of the joint of a dystrophic nature with damage to the articular cartilage. Words formed by simultaneously adding a prefix and a suffix to the root are called prefix-suffix derivatives. Thus, in ancient Greek terminology, the terms hypo-gastr-ium lower abdomen arose. It should be taken into account that Latin prefixes are attached to Latin roots, Greek prefixes are added to Greek roots.

Prefixation does not change the meaning of the term, but only adds to the meaning some component indicating localization (above, below, in front, behind), direction, passage in time, the absence or negation of something. For example, exoglossia is an enlargement of the tongue when it protrudes significantly from the mouth, dysergia is a disorder of the body's reactivity, aphonia is a lack of sonority of the voice.

Suffixes have an important classifying function. Thanks to them, words are correlated with the corresponding classes of concepts: for example, nouns with the suffixes -ul-, -cul- belong to the class of so-called deminutives - words with a diminutive meaning: tuberculum, lobulus. A suffix always exists only in a bound form, i.e. as part of a derivative. For example, the suffix -itis (inflammation) only in combination with a productive base acquires the above meaning. When suffixing, the stems of different parts of speech - nouns, adjectives, verbs - are used as generators. Certain suffixes are combined with the stems of certain parts of speech, for example, the suffix -al(-ar) with the stems of nouns, the suffixes -io, -or with verbal stems.

Compound words are formed by adding two or more roots. Greek roots of words are connected using an interfix (connecting vowel) -o- or can be without it, for example, proct-o-plexia - fixation of the rectum when it prolapses, pneumon-ectomy - complete removal of the lung, phleb-o-gramma - x-ray image of the venous network.

Clinical terminology contains, along with words of Greek origin, terms of Latin origin, for example, resection, onis f - removal of part of an organ, ulcus, eris n - ulcer, etc. There are also hybrid terms consisting of Latin and Greek term elements, for example, dysfunctio, onis f - dysfunction, tonsillitis, itidis f - inflammation of the palatine tonsils.

CONCLUSION

To correctly compose terms, it is necessary to learn both the initial and final term elements and their meaning. You also need to know the rules for placing stress. In clinical terms of Greek origin ending in -ia, the stress is most often placed on the penultimate syllable, for example,

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-2

nephrectomía, hemiplegía, etc. On the third syllable from the end of the word, the stress is placed in the final term element –logia: biológia, ophthalmológia, etc. Term elements – pathia, -graphia, -phonia in medical terminology have the stress on the penultimate syllable, and in the terminology of other disciplines they keep it on the third syllable from the end of the word, for example, roentgenographía, but photography, mastopathía, but sympáthia, etc.

LITERATURES:

1. Mukhamadiyeva, M., & Sharipov, B. (2022). LATIN AS THE MAIN LANGUAGE OF MEDICINE. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 1(7), 337-339.
2. Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE FORMATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(6), 477-479.
3. Sharipov, B. (2022). RETSIPROKLIK XUSUSIDA MULOHAZALAR. *Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 1(19), 63-66.
4. Salimovich, S. B. (2022). RECIPROCAL SYMMETRY AND ITS GRAMMATICAL INDICATIONS. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*, 7(12), 129-131.
5. Salimovich, S. B. (2022). Studies of Reciprocity in Linguistics. *Eurasian Scientific Herald*, 8, 221-224.
6. Isroilova, M., & Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME OBSERVATIONS ON LATIN PRONUNCIATION AND SPELLING. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(7), 127-129.
7. Шарипов, Б. С. (2022). TIL BIRLIKLARINING NUTQDA FAOLLASHUVI HAQIDA. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 5(1).
8. Nasimjanovna, K. F., & Salimovich, S. B. (2023). NAMES OF DISEASES AND THEIR USE IN CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(6), 469-474.
9. Salimovich, S. B. (2022, January). FUNCTIONS OF LANGUAGE UNITS. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 62-63).
10. Mardanovich, M. Z., Aliaskarovna, S. U., Kenjaevna, B. M., Genjebaevna, A. P., & Salimovich, S. B. (2021). Some Considerations about Legal Solutions and Practices of Certain Problems Writing Recipes. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 5341-5352.
11. ZAFAR, M., BOBUR, S., & DILMUROD, B. R. (2021). Scientific and pedagogical basis of teaching the theory of decisions in school chemistry. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 1(3), 192-196.
12. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). The role of teaching latin in the course of subject training of future foreign language teachers. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(1), 11-14.
13. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). Features of teaching latin to students medical universities studying in english. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(1), 21-25.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-2

14. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). Influence of the latin language on the formation of medical terminology. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(1), 16-20.
15. Maxmudov, Z., Sharipov, B., & Bo'riyev, D. (2023). Tibbiyot universitetlarida lotin tili va tibbiy terminologiya fanini o'qitishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(1), 5-10.
16. Maxmudov, Z. M., & Sharipov, B. S. (2021). LOTIN TILI VA TIBBIY TERMINOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING DIDAKTIK TAMOYILLARI VA UNING ASOSI HAQIDA FIKRLAR. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(6), 1028-1033.
17. Maxmudov, Z. M., & Sharipov, B. S. LOTIN TILI VA TIBBIY TERMINOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING DIDAKTIK TAMOYILLARI VA UNING ASOSI HAQIDA FIKRLAR.
18. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimovich, S. B., & Arzimurodovich, B. D. (2021). Developing Students Attitudes Towards the Environment When Teaching a Foreign Languages. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 1(1), 199-201.
19. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimovich, S. B., & Arzimurodovich, B. D. (2021). Reviews of effective use of educational methods in teaching latin and medical terminology. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 381-386.
20. Mardanovich, M. Z., & Salimovich, S. B. Auditoriyadan tashqari ta'lim-tarbiyaga maqsadli, tizimli yondashish. In *Конференция состоялась 5 марта 2022 года на базе Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института по адресу: Республика Узбекистан, 100047, г. Ташкент, ул. Махтумкули, 103. Цель конференции—знакомство и обмен опытом в обучении и в работе с цифровыми данными, технологиями их применения в гуманитарных* (p. 455).
21. Mardanovich, M. Z., & Salimovich, S. B. (2022, August). AUDITORIYADAN TASHQARI TA'LIM-TARBIYAGA MAQSADLI, TIZIMLI YONDASHISH: Mahmudov Zafar Mardanovich Samarqand davlat tibbiyot instituti, Tillar kafedrası, assistent, e-mail: maxmudovzafar4510@ gmail. com Sharipov Bobur Salimovich Samarqand davlat tibbiyot instituti, Tillar kafedrası, assistent, e-mail: sharipovbobur9689@ gmail. com Bo'riyev Dilmurod Arzimurodovich Samarqand davlat tibbiyot instituti, Tillar kafedrası, stajyor-assistent buriyev. d0905@ gmail. com. In *Научно-практическая конференция*.
22. Maxmudov, Z. M. (2021). Bobur Salimovich Sharipov Lotin tili va tibbiy terminologiya fanini o'qitishda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanishning didaktik tamoyillari va uning asosi haqida fikrlar. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 6.